

NIRC2-Pol Operations Guide

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General NIRC2 observer's manual (including directions for QACITS) can be found [here](#).

Instructions for mini-QACITS are in development at this doc: [📄 miniQACITS_manual_v2](#)

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NIRC2 Polarimetry Specs

NIRC2 Polarimetry (NIRC2-Pol, or nirc2p) is a dual-channel polarimetry mode on the Keck II NIRC2 infrared imager. Dual-channel polarimetry uses a polarizing beamsplitter to split the incoming light into two orthogonal polarization states, and a half-wave plate (HWP) to modulate the angle of polarization. Through cycles of four critical HWP angles (0° , 45° , 22.5° , 67.5°), it is possible to recover the linear Stokes vector components Q and U (see [de Boer+ 2020](#) for a description of dual-channel polarimetry and double differencing).

NIRC2-Pol enables polarimetric observations in $JHKL'$ bands in combination with multiple existing NIRC2 modes, such as grism spectroscopy and high-contrast coronagraphic imaging, and both NGS and LGS AO. This is useful for many science cases, from solar system objects to circumstellar disks and active galactic nuclei. NIRC2-Pol was developed as part of the Precision Calibration Unit (PCU2) project on Keck II.

PCU2/NIRC2-Pol Optical Path and Stages

NIRC2-Pol relies on two additional optics in the Keck II AO bench and NIRC2: a half-wave plate (HWP), located in the Precision Calibration Unit (PCU2), and a Wollaston prism, located in the outer NIRC2 filter wheel. The PCU2 is an analogous optomechanical set-up to the Pinhole Calibration Unit (PCU1) on Keck I (Claveau+ 2026), with linear and rotation stages to move optics into the beam.

Figure 1: (Left) Cartoon of Keck II optics illustrating where the two key pieces for NIRC2-Pol (HWP and Wollaston beamsplitter) are located. (Right) Diagram of the K2 AO Bench with the approximate PCU location noted.

The PCU2 has a mount that can hold one optic at a time out of the following options: a pinhole mask for astrometric calibration, a half-wave plate for J/H/K-band polarimetric observations, or a half-wave plate for L' polarimetric observations. To switch between these three, **the optic in the PCU2 must be manually switched by Keck staff**. A document detailing the HWP swap procedures is [available here](#) and in internal Keck documentation. This swap procedure is a limiting factor for observations, and must be accounted for in proposals and observation planning, as Keck staff require significant notice to plan and perform this task (see [Proposing for NIRC2-Pol](#) and [Observation Planning](#) in this guide for more information). The HWPs for NIRC2-Pol are stored in a protective Pelican case in the K2 AO enclosure.

In the K2 AO diagram above, there are two additional optics worth noting, as they must be removed from the beam for NIRC2-Pol: the KPIC Pickoff Dichroic Stage (#8, DFB) and the NIRSPA0 pickoff mirror (#7, ISM). There is also an IR transmissive dichroic (#6), which may affect polarimetric calibration—characterization of its polarimetric properties is currently in progress.

The linear stages in the PCU2 can move in the x and y directions; the HWPs/pinhole mask are located on the upper z stage, while a calibration fiber is located on the lower z stage. There are limits to how far you can move the stages in each direction to prevent collisions within the enclosed space of the AO bench; these limits and the measured center points are detailed in a document called PCU_motor_configurations.yaml on the k2aoserver computers. Currently, the HWP can move 20mm from the center in the x and y directions at any of the allowable z positions.

The HWPs are also located in a rotation stage. This rotation stage uses a relative encoder; although the device has an incremental encoder, a referencing procedure at start up makes it such that the absolute position is the same each time it is commanded within $\pm 54 \mu\text{s}$. Accordingly, we can assume that the HWP's absolute position is consistent across uses; however, when the HWPs are swapped, we take a calibration sequence to confirm the position of the fast axis of the HWP each time it is installed. We also recommend taking this fast axis daytime calibration set for each night of observing if time allows. The fast axis calibration is detailed as part of the NIRC2-Pol calibration procedure (see [Daytime Calibrations](#)).

NIRC2-Pol's Wollaston prism is located inside NIRC2 (in the outer filter wheel), and it also relies on a 5x10" field mask in NIRC2's slit and mask sliders to reduce the FOV such that the ordinary and extraordinary beams from the Wollaston beamsplitter do not overlap.

Figure 2: An illustration of the 5x10" focal plane mask and the orientation of the ordinary and extraordinary beams (orthogonal polarization states) on the detector.

HWP Specs

Figure 3: The unmounted NIRC2-Pol HWPs.

The JHK waveplate was fabricated by Bernard Halle and is effective over the wavelength range 1100-2400 nm. It is an achromatic half wave retarder made of two plates, one quartz (1.48 mm thickness) and one MgF_2 (1.16 mm thickness), with an air gap and four spacers. The fast axis is marked with dots on the side surface, and the waveplate has a clear aperture of 53 mm. The quartz side of the JHK HWP is coated with [TelAztek RAR](#) Nano-Texture.

The L' waveplate was fabricated by the Karl Lambrecht Corporation and is effective over the wavelength range 3420-4130 nm. It is a zero order double plate air spaced MgF_2 half wave retarder (2.75 mm thickness) with a clear aperture of 53 mm.

Both waveplates were characterized in the lab at UCSB by Will Melby, Rebecca Zhang, and Ryan Hersey ([Melby+ 2024](#)).

Throughput

The throughput of the JHK HWP is over 92% across the wavelength range tested (1100-1900 nm), and is predicted to be this high or better at longer wavelengths, according to theoretical values from the manufacturer.

We report throughput values as the percentage of the relative flux reaching the camera after the insertion of the waveplate. Measurements are taken for each wavelength at 25 positions on the waveplate. We additionally take a reference measurement at each wavelength without the waveplate inserted, and finally a dark frame for background subtraction. Each measurement, dark, and calibration (air measurement) consists of 100 frames.

To prevent fluctuations in laser output affecting the reported number, we feed a fraction of the laser to a photodiode to measure the laser output during each frame. Photodiode measurements are normalized such that the highest measurement per wavelength is 1. Frames are normalized by dividing each pixel by the normalized photodiode reading. See 'Throughput_Notebook.ipynb' and 'Throughput_Module.py' in the [NIRC2-Pol GitHub](#) for a full detailed walkthrough.

Figure 3 shows the average throughput across the 25 positions with error bars of 1 standard deviation.

Figure 4: Throughput of the JHK HWP as measured in the UCSB MAPL lab (left) and theoretical values pre- and post-AR coating from the vendor (right).

The throughput of the L' HWP is not currently characterized due to the lack of lab infrastructure at its specified wavelength range. Manufacturing specifications put the L' HWP throughput at >90% across its effective wavelength range.

Retardance

The manufacturer specification for the JHK HWP retardance is $\lambda/2 \pm \lambda/70$. For L', we took measurements in the lab between 1-2 microns and extrapolated to L' wavelengths and found less than $\lambda/5$ across L' band.

Figure 5: Retardance of the JHK HWP (left) and L' HWP (right).

Vignetting and Centering

Vignetting is not a major issue for NIRC2-Pol, and should not appear for the nominal center location for the HWPs where they are positioned for standard NIRC2-Pol observations. Vignetting appears at x values lower than ~ 100 mm and greater than ~ 124 mm.

For $z=0$, the HWP is centered on NIRC2 when the PCU2 is at [110.05, 186.35, 0.0, 0.0]. This is saved in the PCU Sequencer GUI as `hwp_jhk_z_0`. This position was used in commissioning.

The nominal z-location for the HWP is $z=43$. The HWP is centered on NIRC2 when the PCU2 is at [110.05, 185.94, 43.0, 0.0]. This is saved in the PCU Sequencer as `hwp_center` and is the recommended center position for all standard observations.

Polarimetric Efficiency

Polarimetric efficiency depends on the image rotator (IMR / K-mirror) position, due to the high angle of incidence on these mirrors (which converts linear polarization to circular, which cannot be measured by our instrumental setup). Initial analysis of commissioning data as shown in Figure 6 suggests that an image rotator angle of 0 has the *lowest* polarimetric efficiency and should therefore be avoided. The highest efficiency is around 45 degrees for JHK bands, and efficiency is relatively constant across L' (where the IMR is not as effective as a half-wave plate).

Figure 6: Relative polarimetric efficiency for various IMR and HWP angles. Each curve is normalized to its highest point.

Available Modes

A variety of modes are available for use with polarimetry. See below for each possible mode and its current status in commissioning.

Mode	Possible?	Commissioning Status
JHK Polarimetric Imaging	Yes	Successfully tested on-sky
L' Polarimetric Imaging	Yes	Successfully tested on-sky
JHK Coronagraphic Polarimetric Imaging (Lyot)	Yes	Successfully tested on-sky (300 mas Lyot)
L' Coronagraphic Polarimetric Imaging (Lyot)	Yes	Successfully tested on-sky (300 mas Lyot)
JHK Coronagraphic Polarimetric Imaging (Vortex)	Yes	On-sky testing scheduled for May 2026; data processing procedure requires further work due to the vortex's complex polarimetric properties
L' Coronagraphic Polarimetric Imaging (Vortex)	Yes	Successfully tested on-sky, but data processing procedure requires further work due to the vortex's complex polarimetric properties
JHK Spectropolarimetry	Yes	Not yet tested; theoretically possible but NIRC2 grism modes have not been used recently
L' Spectropolarimetry	Yes	Not yet tested; theoretically possible but NIRC2 grism modes have not been used recently

Narrow-Band Polarimetric Imaging	Maybe	Many of the narrow band filters are located on the same filter wheel as the Wollaston, and therefore are incompatible. Narrow-band imaging is only possible with the filters that are on the <i>inner</i> filter wheel.
Sparse Aperture Masking with Polarimetry	No	The 9-hole mask is on the same filter wheel as the Wollaston prism. Other combinations are disallowed for similar reasons; see the FAQ for which filters are on the same wheel as the Wollaston.

AO Performance in Pol Mode

Keck II Adaptive Optics (AO) can be used with NIRC2-Pol as with standard NIRC2 operations, with minor impacts on the Strehl ratio.

NGS AO

From commissioning observations, we had an average Strehl of $56.6 \pm 0.9\%$ with standard NIRC2 observations and an average Strehl of $52.0 \pm 2.2\%$ with NIRC2-Pol observations (JHK HWP, $5 \times 10''$ mask, and Wollaston in); we note that seeing degraded slightly throughout the course of these observing sequences (from $\sim 0.20''$ to $\sim 0.24''$), with high cirrus clouds intermittently present, which may explain the slight discrepancy between the average Strehls.

Strehl is noticeably worse with polarimetry in L' band. During commissioning, we observed an average Strehl of $40.3 \pm 2.7\%$ with the polarimetric optics, and an average of $47.2 \pm 4.2\%$ without, as measured by the Strehl tool in the NIRC2 Quicklook. Removing the HWP did not improve Strehl, indicating that NCPAs from the Wollaston are a likely culprit for the degradation of the correction. After the HAKA upgrade, a brief test noted a larger degradation of Strehl in L' ($\sim 71\%$ with the pol optics, $\sim 80\%$ without, as measured by the AO team), with a notable ($\sim 2\%$) difference between the ordinary and extraordinary beams.

LGS AO

Commissioning tests reveal similar degradation of Strehl in L' band with the polarimetric optics for LGS AO. We observed an average Strehl of $18.8 \pm 4.1\%$ with the polarimetric optics, and an average of $25.8 \pm 5.3\%$ without. The field of regard is approximately $30''$ with the HWP in position, and so that places constraints on choices of tip/tilt stars; note that using an off-axis tip tilt star requires position angle mode for the rotator, regardless of whether or not you are using pol mode. The L' HWP reduces the laser throughput to the WFS camera by approximately ± 0.2 magnitudes, an amount that should not affect LGS performance. LGS AO has not yet been tested with the JHK waveplate. In LGS mode, the HWP may also vignette either STRAP or the SHWFS at its nominal position, depending on the target elevation/PA and IMR angle combination; we recommend defaulting to IMR angles near 45° when possible.

Other AO Methods

[Fast and Furious](#) focal plane wavefront sensing works without any modifications, and during commissioning showed ~5% improvement to the Strehl in L' band; however, F&F is *not* yet released for LGS AO, and so cannot help in that mode. AO image sharpening scripts do not work in their standard forms at present with pol mode after the recent HAKA upgrade, but are likely to be updated in the near future. The standard image sharpening scripts (i.e. no Wollaston in the beam) are generally still useful, as the differential coma appears to be roughly equal between both polarimetric beams. It is worth noting that initial commissioning observations have noticeable differences between the speckles in the ordinary and extraordinary beams in coronagraphic observations, but the speckles appear relatively stable between HWP rotations.

KTL Keywords and EPICS Channels for PCU/NIRC2-Pol

PCU2 stages containing the HWPs can be controlled with [EPICS channels](#) on k2aosever or [KTL keywords](#) on k2aosever or waikoko-new (*not* vm-nirc2). Headers were added 12/4/2025 — data before this date (i.e. from commissioning) has the HWP information in the object names or in an observing log. Relevant EPICS channels and their corresponding KTL keywords are below:

EPICS	KTL	Description
K2:ao:pcu:m1Pos	PCUX (or PCUM1POS)	PCU X position
K2:ao:pcu:m2Pos	PCUY (or PCUM2POS)	PCU Y position
K2:ao:pcu:m3Pos	PCUPZ (or PCUM3POS)	PCU Upper Z position (HWP)
k2:ao:pcu:m4Pos	PCUZ (or PCUM4POS)	PCU Lower Z position
k2:ao:pcu:stst	PCUSTST	PCU Status
k2:ao:pcu:state	PCUSTAT	PCU State
k2:ao:pcu:posRb	PCUNAME	PCU named position
k2:ao:pcu:rot:connected	PCURCON	Rotation stage connection status
k2:ao:pcu:rot:stat	PCURSTAT	Rotation stage status
k2:ao:pcu:rot:pos	PCURNAME	Rotation stage named position
k2:ao:pcu:rot:posval	PCUPR	Rotation stage position, degrees
k2:ao:pcu:rot:vel	PCURVEL	Rotation stage velocity, degrees/sec (default

		180 deg/sec)
k2:ao:pcu:rot:acc	PCURACC	Rotation stage acceleration, deg/sec/sec (default 1000 deg/sec/sec)

Generally, EPICS channels can be accessed by the `caget` command, where you add `Rb` to the end of the channel to indicate that you're reading back the existing value. See [DIY Observing](#) and [Manually Moving the PCU](#) for additional information on how to interact with the PCU via EPICS and KTL. Other particularly relevant keywords to NIRC2-Pol that exist for all NIRC2 observations are:

- `FILT` = filter combination
- `FWONAME` = outer filter, *for polarimetry should always be Wollaston*
- `FWINAME` = inner filter
- `SLMNAME` = mask name, *for polarimetry should always be 5arcsec_wide*
- `OBDBNAME` = tells us whether the DFB is in (see [PCU Stages](#) for more details)
- `OBIMNAME` = tells us whether ISM is in (see [PCU Stages](#) for more details)
- `OBOFNAME` = tells us whether OFM is in
- `ROTPOSN` = image rotator position (see [FAQ](#) for more information on the multiple keywords related to the image rotator and its movement)
- `ROTMODE` = image rotator mode (e.g. VERTANG, POSANG)

Other Notes

The JHK HWP was damaged in transit to Keck, and as a result has a small crack on the edge of the plate. This defect is likely not in the beam path with standard target placement in the center of the field. Future commissioning observations will further explore the effect of this defect and resulting limits on target placement.

Integration of NIRC2-Pol into Keck facilities is ongoing, and it is being offered as a non-facility visitor instrument in 26B. See below for a summary of the status of various steps of facility integration:

Integration Task	Status
Relevant PCU keywords saved in FITS headers for NIRC2-Pol observations	Implemented
NIRC2-Pol data products are properly ingested into KOA and relevant keywords are searchable	Implemented
NIRC2 observer accounts have a GUI to check the HWP and PCU status	Implemented
NIRC2-Pol is incorporated into SciAS	Not yet implemented

NIRC2-Pol is an instrument option on the Keck proposal cover sheets	Implemented
NIRC2-Pol is incorporated into observatory scheduling procedures	Implemented (at least for proposal scheduling)
NIRC2-Pol operations scripts are added to and maintained on observatory SVN	Not yet implemented

Instructions for Observing

This section contains detailed info on all aspects of NIRC2-Pol Observing – if you would like a quick reference list of what to do, please see [Quick Start Checklists](#).

NIRC2-Pol Scripts/Software

All scripts for operating NIRC2-Pol (including executing observing sequences, taking calibration data) will be housed in the [NIRC2Pol-Ops GitHub repository](#). As of 4/29/2026, these are available on Keck systems using waikoko-new under `/home/nirc2eng/vis/maxmb`; however, they will soon be added to the observatory SVN and made available via standard procedures to users. Before integration into SVN, the scripts are accessible if you use the `user maxmb` command as indicated in setup. These scripts are generally intended to be run on waikoko-new, but may also be compatible with k2aoserver. Versions with `_epics` are intended to be run on k2aoserver-new, as they use EPICS commands instead of KTL keywords. Software for data processing and calibration are currently under development and will be available soon on the [NIRC2Pol-DPP repository](#) (see [Data Processing](#) for more information).

If you write custom observing scripts, you can reference [this Keck webpage](#) to use `scp` to move scripts to the Keck computers. If you are running the remote observing software with `./start_keck_viewers`, your local machine will be within the Keck firewall. Your program PI should have a directory on `/home/nirc2eng/vis/[your username here]` — when within the firewall, you can scp to this writable directory using your assigned account (e.g. `nirc4`) and a password provided by your SA. If you do not know your username, ask your SA. When logged in for observing, you can add your files to the path with `user [your username here]` on waikoko-new.

Proposing for NIRC2-Pol

As mentioned in [PCU2/NIRC2-Pol Optical Path and Stages](#), switching between the JHK and L' HWP's requires a **manual swap** performed at the summit by Keck staff. This means you **cannot observe with both JHK and L' polarimetry in a single night**.

This consideration is taken into account at the proposal scheduling level, and potential observers must note the instrument request on the cover sheet in the standard way (available

options are [nirc2pLGS-JHK](#), [nirc2pNGS-JHK](#), [nirc2pLGS-L](#), and [nirc2pNGS-L](#) for the various configurations). If you do not indicate NIRC2-Pol on your proposal and want to switch to this mode, you will need to contact the scheduler; similar to switching from NGS AO to LGS, the more advance notice you provide, the more likely it is that Keck will be able to accommodate your request.

As NIRC2-Pol is not yet fully supported as a facility mode, we recommend that you discuss your planned observations with the project team (Max Millar-Blanchaer maxmb@ucsb.edu, Rebecca Zhang manxuanzhang@ucsb.edu, Briley Lewis brileylewis@ucsb.edu) to ensure that your observations are feasible. Additional information on the limitations and achievable polarimetric accuracies of the mode will be provided in this guide as soon as it is available.

Observation Planning

Starlists

Follow the [standard NIRC2 instructions for planning star lists](#), and/or use the standard tools for star list creation on the [Keck user homepage](#). LGS targets must be submitted early for approval by the Laser Clearinghouse; your SA should communicate this deadline to you, but it is approximately a week minimum before observations. We recommend including both the V and R magnitudes in your starlists (using [Vmag=](#) and [Rmag=](#) in the star list tool notes), as V is used for the OA and telescope positioning in [MAGIQ](#), while R is used for AO. See [this FAQ](#) for how to add a non-sidereal target.

Overheads

With NIRC2-Pol observations, we have to account for the extra time to take HWP cycles for our observations. See below for an updated equation to estimate the total observing time:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total elapsed observing time(sec)} = & 6*(ndither+1) + \\ & (12+4+1)*ndither*nframes*ncycles + \\ & 4*ndither*nframes*ncycles*coadds*(itime + tread*(nread-1)) \end{aligned}$$

where:

- nframes = number of frames per HWP cycle per dither
- coadds = number of coadds
- itime = tint = individual integration
- tread = nirc2 readout time (0.18sec for full array 1024x1024 ; 0.05 for sub-array 512x512)
- nread = number of reads (n=2 for CDS, n=n for MCDS)
- ncycles = number of HWP cycles
- 6 sec is the AO overhead during dither (open loops, move telescope, reposition Field Steering Mirrors (FSMs), reposition WFS focus (FCS), close TT loop, close DM loop).
- 12 sec is the time to read and write a NIRC2 image including FITS information.

- 2 sec is the time for the HWP rotation command; the rotation stage moves quickly, but this includes time for the command to be processed and sent to the stage. The factor of 4 is for the 4 HWP angles needed in a cycle.

An additional overhead of a few seconds (<5-10 secs) may occur, maybe once every 20 dither moves, when repositioning the FCS or the FSMs. Changing filters and cameras takes at minimum 16 to 22 seconds. Setting integration time and checking saturation takes ~2-4 minutes, as does positioning a target behind a coronagraphic mask. Occasionally, NIRC2 will simply take longer to move filters and masks—consider budgeting at least 5 minutes each time you need to make substantial changes to the observing configuration as a “conservative” plan.

We also provide an [online calculator GUI](#) for quick estimates of the time for one HWP cycle given your observing parameters.

Factors to Consider for L' Observations

Observing in L' presents many challenges due to the substantially higher thermal background. Dome flats are possible since the thermal background is significantly attenuated by the HWP and Wollaston, but it is unclear how effective they are, so please use them with caution. We instead suggest using sky flats, or (for polarimetric calibration) unpolarized standard stars. The thermal background changes on quite short timescales and significant effort is required to remove this effect, as described in [Nguyen et al. 2025](#). Efficiency is also *much* lower at this wavelength, and time should be budgeted accordingly.

We recommend:

- Taking sky flats/backgrounds with each target for 3 HWP cycles. You can do this by moving the target slightly off the detector with the `xy` dither command.
 - Sky flats are blank frames of just the sky background where there are no targets present in the field; these are much more effective at flat fielding than dome flats.
 - Sky flats work best when they match both the integration time and coadds of the science frames (regardless of whether or not you are near the saturation limit of the detector)
 - These also can be used for sky subtraction, but this is not recommended unless you are subtracting a short sequence (ie: very little elevation change) since the background brightness is a function of the elevation. Humidity levels change the background randomly throughout the night so there will always be leftover background signal even after sky subtraction.
 - Dithering during observations — we provide the option for an ABBA dither in the observing script, and further details in [Dithering with NIRC2-Pol](#).
 - The dithering cadence is dependent on the elevation and how quickly the thermal background changes. The faster it changes the more dithers you may need.

These two calibrations are necessary for effective removal of the thermal background; however, they do lower observing efficiency significantly and must be considered in planning. Note that

dithering is not possible with coronagraphic observations, as the masks are fixed on the detector.

Signal-to-Noise Ratio Calculations

When planning observations, remember that the light is being split by the Wollaston prism, so you will have approximately half the counts you'd normally expect for each image on the detector (in addition to any reduction in [throughput](#) from the additional optics). [Nguyen+ 2021](#) outlines the framework for polarimetric SNR calculations and exposure time necessary to reach a given polarimetric accuracy.

Choosing Polarimetric Standard Stars

A number of observations of polarimetric standard stars have already been executed using NIRC2-Pol for commissioning and calibration (e.g. the creation of the system [Mueller Matrix model](#)); a list of these observations, their dates, and the resulting updates to the calibration are presented in this document: [NIRC2-Pol Polarimetric Calibration Standards](#).

A number of factors can influence the instrumental polarization, including new optics, changes in position of optics, degradation of optical coatings, and more. Currently, we do not yet have a strong sense of what factors are likely to change and on what timescales for NIRC2-Pol; accordingly, if your goals include *quantitative* polarimetry, we recommend observing at least two unpolarized and two polarized standard stars as part of your observations. These observations are likely to take approximately two hours (30 min per target). However, if your science goals only require more qualitative polarimetry (e.g. circumstellar disk morphology), you likely do not need to take this extra calibration data. The [ZetaPersei package](#) ([Zhang+ 2025](#)) has functionality to choose both unpolarized and polarized standard stars near your science targets from the Whittet (1992) and Heiles (2000) catalogs.

Impacts of Twilight on Polarimetric Observations

The sky background during daytime and twilight is polarized due to sunlight scattering off dust, air molecules, and aerosols in the atmosphere. The degree of polarization depends on the angle between the sky position of interest and the Sun, with the highest degree of polarization generally at 90° —and the sky polarization can be substantial, up to approximately 80% (massive compared to typical astronomical polarization signals, which are often on the order of a few percent at most). The degree of sky polarization also depends on the wavelength of observation, generally most highly polarized in visible light around 700 nm ([Postlyakov 2003](#), [Eshelman and Shaw 2018](#)) and therefore less of an issue at the infrared wavelengths of NIRC2-Pol. Near sunset and sunrise, the highest polarization is generally a band across the sky passing near zenith perpendicular to the Sun ([Zhao et al. 2018](#)).

Previous work suggests that the visible light sky polarization from sunlight should appear/disappear ~45 min to an hour from sunrise and sunset respectively. This is around 10-20 minutes *after* the onset of astronomical twilight at dawn, or 10-20 minutes *before* the onset of

astronomical twilight at dusk ([Cronin et al. 2005, 2006](#)). Accordingly, we recommend waiting until **astronomical twilight** to conduct polarimetric observations; we plan to soon explore the sky polarization on Mauna Kea in infrared light in more detail as part of NIRC2-Pol commissioning.

Other Settings to Consider

Consider which detector settings to use for your observations. There is more information on this in the [NIRC2 Observer's Manual](#). From commissioning observations, we think that *MCDS* (multiple correlated double sampling) is preferable to *CDS* (correlated double sampling) for avoiding fixed pattern noise on the detector that may limit observations.

As mentioned in a previous section on [Polarimetric Efficiency](#), the image rotator (IMR / K-mirror) position must be considered as it affects observations, converting some linearly polarized light into circularly polarized light, depending on its angle.

Daytime / Sky Flat Calibrations

L' band observations require sky flats, as the dome is too bright and will saturate the detector. For JHK bands, you can take dome flats in the afternoon before or the morning after observations; make sure the telescope is parked at the dome flat position, as a change in angle does affect the polarization of M3. For dome flats, be sure to use the *spectral* lamp, as it is brighter.

With any NIRC2-Pol polarimetric imaging observations, complete at minimum the following calibrations in bold, and consider adding additional calibrations depending on your science case:

- **Darks:** Take for each set of detector settings (coadds, tint, sampmode) that you used for your observations.
- **Standard Flats:** Take standard flats for each filter you use; some recommend taking additional flats that also include the pupil mask (e.g. largehex) and/or coronagraph that you used in observations
- **Polarimetric Flats:** Same as standard flats, but with the NIRC2-Pol hardware (Wollaston, field mask, HWP) in the beam. These are taken with the HWP continuously rotating, and will correct for any additional aberrations in the field from the polarization-related optics.
- [Recommended] Collect HWP rotation sequence to verify fast axis orientation.
- [Optional] Collect internal calibration data for instrumental polarization calibration Mueller Matrix model update.

To take the basic standard calibrations, you can take the DIY approach (instructions below) or we have scripts available in user `maxmb: Darks_Script.sh` and `Flats_Script.sh`. The darks script will automatically pull needed exposure times and other parameters from the data folder you specify with `bash Darks_Script.sh <data_folder> <output_script_folder>`.

For flats, you only need to provide the needed filter as `bash Flats_Script.sh FILT=[filter]`. If you have set `pupilhex=true` for your observations, as we recommend having the largehex mask, make sure to insert that when you set up for flats. The user is responsible for running `configA0forFlats` or doing those steps manually before running the flats script. The time required for darks depends heavily on the number of combinations of settings you use, while flats take approximately 15 minutes per wavelength filter J/H/L or 30 minutes for K due to the longer integration times.

Instructions for Taking Darks

For darks, you only need to have control over the NIRC2 instrument — the telescope does not have to be at any particular position, and you do not need access to the PCU2 or any other parts of the AO bench.

1. Let the OA/SA know you plan to take darks.
2. If you haven't yet, update the observer info on the PIG and update the directory with `newdir`.
3. Close the NIRC2 shutter with `shutter close`
4. Change the object name to "Dark" with `object dark`
5. Configure to the desired detector settings (with `tint`, `coadd`, and `sampmode` as usual).
6. Take at least 3-5 darks for each set of detector settings needed, i.e. using `bash Darks_Script.sh <data_folder> <output_script_folder>`

Instructions for Taking Standard and Polarimetric Dome Flats

These instructions are adapted from the [original NIRC2 guide to dome flats](#).

1. Make sure NIRC2 is the instrument selected using the FACSUM GUI; if it is not, ask the OA to select NIRC2.
2. If you haven't yet, open the NIRC2 Status GUI to check the program ID. If it is not correct, update the observer info on the PIG and update the night's directory with `newdir`.
3. Ask the OA to move to the dome flat position. FACSUM should show the telescope stowed at El = 45, Az = 64 and say "DOME FLATS."
4. Open a new terminal for waikoko-new (right click and a drop down menu will appear).
5. In the command line on vm-nirc2 or waikoko-new, type `configA0forFlats` and answer Y. Note, if you are taking afternoon calibrations, check with the SA before doing this—in the morning, you may proceed without the SA. This command moves the AO cal fiber, DFB, OFM, and ISM out of the path and opens the AO hatch. If this command is not working, please refer to [this FAQ for manual setup](#).

IF TAKING STANDARD FLATS WITH FLATS_SCRIPT.SH:

6. Run the flats script for each filter needed with `bash Flats_Script.sh`
`FILT=[filter]`

IF TAKING STANDARD FLATS MANUALLY:

6. Next, notify the summit crew that you are going to take dome flats using `modify -s dcs domecals=true`
7. Using the K2 Flat Lamps Control GUI turn on the spectral lamps for dome flats. Right Click → K2 Telescope Status Menu → Dome Lamp Control. You can also turn on/off the lamps via the command line: `modify -s dcs flimagin=0 flspectr=1` turns on the spectral lamps and `modify -s dcs flimagin=0 flspectr=0` turns them off.

8. Make sure you have the NIRC2 narrow camera selected (`camera narrow`)
9. Open the NIRC2 shutter with `shutter open`
10. Change the object name to “Flat” with `object flat`
11. Take at least 3-5 flats per filter needed, using the recommended exposure times below (set this with `tint`, `coadd`, and `sampmode` as usual). Make sure you have the right `subc` subarray size and `filter` for your needs. These are your standard flat-fielding files.

FOR TAKING POL FLATS [RECOMMENDED]:

12. Set the IMR angle to maximum polarimetric efficiency with `modify -s A0.OBRT=45`
13. Run the pol flats script for each filter needed with `bash Polarimetric_Flats.sh`
`FILT=[filter]`

AFTER TAKING FLATS

14. Turn off the dome lamps. (Done in script, if used)
15. Notify the summit crew you have finished with `modify -s dcs domecals=false` (Done in script, if used)
16. Complete [end of night procedures or reset to standard NIRC2 operations](#), if it is morning or evening respectively.

This table contains recommended exposure times for both standard and polarimetric flats. If you are using a filter not included here, please see the NIRC2 Observer’s Manual and estimate the

polarimetric exposure time as ~2x the standard exposure time for flats. L' is included in this table, but may require sky flats to avoid saturation.

Filter	Standard Flats		Polarimetric Flats	
	tint	coadds	tint	coadds
J	20	1	30	1
H	20	1	30	1
K	110	1	120	1
Lp	0.17 (0.5 if on sky)	3	0.17 (0.7 if on sky)	3

Fast Axis Orientation Verification

We recommend verifying the fast axis position of the HWP in two cases: (1) if the HWP was recently swapped into the PCU2 or (2) if your science goals require precise quantitative polarimetric measurements. To determine the HWP fast axis, you must take a sequence of dome flat images at HWP angles ranging from 0 to 180°; we recommend doing this in increments of 10 degrees. The telescope must be parked at dome flat position for this calibration. We provide a script to take this calibration sequence in the [NIRC2Pol-Ops repo](#): [Fast_Axis_Cal_Sequence.sh](#) – to run it, you simply need to provide the desired wavelength filter. This script includes all necessary set up other than notifying the OA/SA and moving the telescope. **Don't forget to take flats/darks for these files!** This sequence takes approximately **one hour**, although will take longer in K band due to the long integration times needed for dome flats. Further information on how this is used in data processing, along with scripts and instructions to manually verify the fast axis angle, are provided in the [Data Processing](#) section of this guide.

Internal Polarimetric Calibration Data

The system's Mueller Matrix model used in the Data Processing Pipeline is created and verified using a set of internal calibration data, which consists of dome flats taken at a series of different HWP and IMR angles. If substantial changes have been made to the K2, AO bench, or NIRC2 optics, it is recommended to take a new set of internal calibration data to verify the instrumental polarization calibration. More information on this calibration can be found in the section [About the Mueller Matrix Model](#), including a list of the prior internal cal sets and when they were taken. Note that taking a full internal calibration sequence takes a substantial amount of dome flat time (approximately 1.5-2.5 hours for one wavelength filter) and therefore may be difficult to schedule. We provide a script to take this calibration sequence again in the [NIRC2Pol-Ops repo](#): [Internal_Pol_Cal_Sequence.sh](#) – to run it, you again just need to provide the wavelength filter. **Don't forget to take flats/darks!** If you are unsure if this calibration is necessary for your observations or would like assistance executing it, please contact the NIRC2-Pol team.

Spectropolarimetry Calibrations

Spectropolarimetry is possible, but has not been officially commissioned. No additional flats are necessary for spectropolarimetry, as NIRC2 historically advises to use imaging flats with spectroscopic data; however, a somewhat involved wavelength calibration will likely be necessary using various internal calibration lamps. From initial testing, we note that the Neon lamp available has sparse features in K band, and moderate in J band.

Setting up NIRC2-Pol

We advise setting up early, well before sunset if you have a first half night (especially given current shutter speed limitations after the Summer 2025 shutter failure). Allow time to troubleshoot the linear and rotation stage commands if needed.

The NIRC2-Pol team plans to provide scripts to automate setup. Until those scripts are available, follow these instructions to set up NIRC2-Pol mode:

1. Complete basic NIRC2 set up.
 - a. Make sure NIRC2 is the instrument selected using the FACSUM GUI; if it is not, ask the OA to select NIRC2.
 - b. Open a new terminal for waikoko-new (right click and a drop down menu will appear). We also recommend opening the NIRC2 Quicklook and Status GUI.
 - c. Open the AO hatch with `ao hatch open`
 - d. Open the NIRC2 shutter with `shutter open`
 - e. Check that DFB, OFM, and ISM are out of beam (`home`) using (a) the SC GUI, (b) `show -s` commands for `ao obdbname`, `ao obimname`, and `obofname`, or (c) reset them all to home with `configA0forFlats` (with the caveat that this last command moves other things on the AO bench).
 - f. Check the program ID on NIRC2 Status GUI. If you haven't yet, update the observer info on the PIG and set the data directory with `newdir`
 - g. Add NIRC2-Pol scripts to path with `user maxmb` (and add path for custom scripts if needed as well).
2. Open a display for polarimetry parameters (the HWP angle, the PCU translation stage position, and whether the 5x10" mask is in) with `xshow -s ao pcupr obrt pcuname -s nirc2 slmname`. If the value for `pcuname` is blank, that means the PCU stages are moving.
3. Check that the HWP is moving properly.
 - a. First, check the current rotator position with `show -s pcu2 PCUPR`
 - b. Next, try to move the rotator with `modify -s pcu2 PCUPR=45`
 - c. Now, see if the rotator actually moved to 45 degrees with `show -s pcu2 PCUPR`.
 - d. If the rotator did not move, see [this FAQ](#) for troubleshooting.

4. Move the PCU2 into position (position `hwp_center`) with `modify -s pcu2 PCUNAME=hwp_center` or using the PCU Sequencer GUI (the latter is only available on k2aoserver).
5. Make sure you have the NIRC2 narrow camera selected (`camera narrow`) – this is the standard operating mode for NIRC2-Pol, although you can [try the wide and medium cameras at your own risk](#).
6. Insert the wollaston and your desired filter with `filter [n] 14` (A full list of wavelength filter names and numbers is provided [in the FAQ here](#).)
7. Insert the 5x10" field mask with `modify -s nirc2 slmname=5arcsec_wide`

Taking On-Sky Observations with NIRC2-Pol

Once NIRC2-Pol is set up:

1. Select the next target in [MAGIQ](#). Ask OA to slew to target.
2. Set the image rotator (IMR) to your preferred mode; we typically use `VERTANG` (i.e. pupil tracking; which is what you would use for ADI) but `POSANG` is also acceptable (i.e. field tracking; and generally preferred for extended solar system objects). Note that IMR angles near zero should be avoided due to [polarimetric efficiency](#). Notify the OA/SA as the AO loop needs to be open for this maneuver (and make sure to do it *before* LGS acquisition), then you can do this with the command `rotate X vertang/posang`
3. Select desired wavelength filter with `filter [n] 14` (A full list of wavelength filter names and numbers is provided [in the FAQ here](#).)
4. [If coronagraph needed] Insert coronagraph (usual user manual commands, i.e. `corona 150` or `vcorona vortexk`) and then re-insert field mask with `modify -s nirc2 slmname = "5arcsec_wide"`
 - a. See [Coronagraphs](#) below for more information on centering.
5. Set desired exposure times with `tint` and `coadd` (and if you want to get more specific with things, you can change your detector settings, e.g. subarraying using `subc` CDS/MCDS, using `sampmode` and `nsamp`)
6. [Optional, but [recommended](#)] Insert the pupil hex mask with `pupil largehex` and make sure it rotates with `pmrrot on`. Pupil tracking in the NIRC2 GUI should be "true" — sometimes this turns off and you may need to restart it. If this does not turn it on, go to a waikoko terminal (*old* waikoko, not new!) and run `nirc2 start pmr`
7. [Optional] If using AO, set `wait4ao on`, unless you do not want the AO correction. If you do not care about the AO correction, you can set `wait4ao off`.
8. Run HWP cycle script with `bash HWP_Rotation_Sequence.sh HWP_CYCLES=[NUM_CYCLES]. [NUM_CYCLES]` sets the number of times the HWP angle sequence is executed (more information about HWP angles below). *If taking sky flats or some other non-science file, use the keyword `IMTYPE=calib`.*

How the Standard Observing Script Works

There is an observing script that will execute standard HWP cycles available on the [NIRC2Pol-Ops repo](#) and on Keck computers at:

```
/home/nirc2eng/vis/maxmb/HWP_Rotation_Sequence.sh
```

HWP cycles for standard Stokes polarimetry include four images, taken at the HWP angles [0°, 45°, 22.5°, 67.5°]. These critical HWP angles are chosen so that 0° and 45° can sample Stokes Q, while 22.5° and 67.5° can sample Stokes U. The script rotates the HWP, checks that it has moved correctly, and then takes an image using the existing integration time and detector settings. In future iterations of the script, the terminal output will be automatically saved; for now, if you would like to save this information, run the HWP cycle script with `command | tee output.txt`

Additional keywords that can be modified outside of this standard observing set-up, executed with `bash HWP_Rotation_Sequence.sh KEYWORD=[KEYWORD VALUE]` are:

1. `OBJ=[OBJECT_NAME]`: The object name saved in the fits file will be overwritten as `OBJECT_NAME`.
2. `ANGLES=[ANGLE_1] [ANGLE_2] ... [ANGLE_N]`: The HWP will modulate from `ANGLE_1` to `ANGLE_N` in the order specified by the list. Angles must be separated by a space.
3. `NUM_EXPOSURES=[NUM_EXPOSURES]`: At each HWP angle, NIRC2 will take [num_exposures] number of images instead of the default of one. All images will have the same settings as displayed in the NIRC2 status GUI.
4. `TOL=[ANGLE_TOLERANCE]`: HWP angle is considered reached when the final angle is within [ANGLE_TOLERANCE] (in degrees) of the next HWP angle in the HWP cycle. The default value is 0.05°.
5. `POLL=[TIME_BETWEEN_POLS]`: The script checks whether the next HWP angle is reached every [TIME_BETWEEN_POLS] seconds. The default value is 0.04s.
6. `IMTYPE=[IMTYPE]`: Defaults to “object.” Can also set to “calib” if doing sky flats or other calibrations. This information is relevant for how files are stored in KOA.

The script detects the existing filter in NIRC2 and does not need to be specified by the user.

Spectropolarimetric Observations

Spectropolarimetric observations have not yet been tested. If you are interested, please refer to the NIRC2 Observer’s Manual documentation on spectroscopy.

Using the Coronagraphs

Any of NIRC2's coronagraphs can be used with NIRC2-Pol. Note that setting a coronagraph with the `corona` or `vcorona` commands will remove the 5x10" field mask, so you will need to move that back in with `modify -s nirc2 slmname=5arcsec_wide` before proceeding with polarimetric observations. Note that the coronagraphs are fixed on NIRC2, so to center the star behind the mask you will need to move the target with a `mov` command or the NIRC2 Quicklook GUI Move Telescope functionality.

Lyot Coronagraphs

Using the Lyot coronagraphs should be relatively straightforward. Centering is performed manually, following the [instructions in the original NIRC2 Observer's Manual](#).

Vortex Coronagraphs

A vortex coronagraph [is itself a spatially-varying polarimetric retarder, making polarimetric data processing challenging](#). However, the vortexes can be used with polarimetry mode. Centering is *not* possible with old editions of the QACITS software, but is possible with the new "[mini-QACITS](#)" developed by Mike Bottom and Mahawa Cisse. It is also possible to take observations manually centering the star on the vortex as is done for the Lyot coronagraphs. Note that there is also vignetting when the vortex is in, which is normal.

See below for the nominal vortex center positions with the Wollaston in:

Coronagraph	Upper Beam Center	Lower Beam Center
vortexk	[326, 696]*	[312, 168]*
vortexlm	[459, 723]	[446, 223]

*The K-band vortex center was measured with the PCU at `hwp_jhk_z_0` not the standard `hwp_center`

Dithering with NIRC2-Pol

NIRC2 has [a number of dither patterns available](#); however, we have currently only integrated a simple ABBA dither into polarimetric observing sequences. This script takes a number of HWP cycles set by the user at position A, double that number at position B, and then another set back at position A. The user will set the dither distance in arcseconds in x and y (e.g. `-3 0`). Negative x moves the star to the right on the detector. To optimize the target's location on the detector (e.g. in the case of extended structures) you may want to change the initial position of the target manually using the telescope move function in the NIRC2 Quicklook GUI. To run the HWP observing script with ABBA dithering, use `bash HWP_Rotation_Sequence.sh XY=[DX DY]`.

Taking Sky Flats

At L', it is also necessary to take sky flats with each target. At this time, we recommend both regular and pol flats. To take these flats:

1. Dither away from your target with `xy # #`
2. Take regular flats
 - a. Remove the Wollaston with `filter 15 17`
 - b. Remove the HWP with `modify -s pcu2 pcuname=home`
 - c. Remove the field mask with `modify -s nirc2 slmname=wide_clear`
 - d. Change the object name with `object SkyFlat`
 - e. Set `tint 0.7` and `coadds 3`
 - f. Set `wait4ao off`
 - g. Take your desired number of flats with `goi`
3. Take pol flats
 - a. Replace the Wollaston with `filter 15 14`
 - b. Move the HWP back in with `modify -s pcu2 pcuname=hwp_center`
 - c. Move the field mask in with `modify -s nirc2 slmname=5arcsec_wide`
 - d. Change the object name with `object SkyPolFlat`
 - e. Set the rotator position with `rotate 89.3 stationary`
 - f. Take your desired number of flats using the sky pol flats script
4. Switch back to `wait4ao on` and dither back to your target. Switch your `tint` and `coadds` back to your science settings and continue.

Manually Moving the PCU2

If you need to manually move the PCU2 from waikoko-new:

- Use the [KTL keywords](#) for the PCU2 with the `modify/show -s pcu2 [keyword]` command structure (i.e. `show -s pcu2 PCUX` and `modify -s pcu2 PCUX=10`)
- If on k2aoserver, you can also use the EPICS `caput` or `caget` commands (i.e. `caget k2:ao:pcu:rot:posvalRb` and `caput k2:ao:pcu:rot:posval 45`) or, for the translation stages, the PCU Sequencer GUI

If moving the translation stages of the PCU2 (i.e. moving the HWP in/out of the beam), alert the SA/OA before making that move, as it briefly vignettes and breaks the AO loop.

If you need to move the HWP continuously (such as is done for flats), set the position value to something high—the limit is 36,000 degrees—and adjust the velocity and acceleration as needed with `rot:vel` and `rot:accel`.

Quick Start Checklists

Part I: NIRC2-Pol Set Up

- Check NIRC2 is selected on FACSUM
- Open waikoko-new terminal
- Open NIRC2 Quicklook
- Open NIRC2 Status GUI
- `ao hatch open`
- `shutter open`
- Make sure that `show -s ao obdbname`, `show -s ao obimname`, and `show -s ao obofname` are all "home"
- Check PIG and update if needed
- Check directory and update if needed with `newdir`
- `user maxmb`
- Open NIRC2-Pol GUI: `xshow -s ao pcupr obrt pcuname -s nirc2 slmname`
- Check HWP motion (`show -s pcu2 PCUPR`, `modify -s pcu2 PCUPR=45`, `show -s pcu2 PCUPR`, [troubleshoot if needed](#))
- `modify -s pcu2 pcuname=hwp_center`
- `camera narrow`
- `modify -s nirc2 slmname=5arcsec_wide`

Part II: Observing

- Select the next target in [MAGIQ](#). Ask OA to slew.
- Set the image rotator (IMR) to your preferred mode (remember to avoid IMR~0 deg) BEFORE AO acquisition
- `filter [n] 14` (see [here for filter list](#))
- `tint`
- `coadd`
- `sampmode / nsamp`
- `subc`
- If no coronagraph:
 - `pupil largehex`
 - `pmrrot on`
- If coronagraph:
 - `pupil fixedhex`
 - Insert coronagraph
 - Re-insert 5x10" mask `modify -s nirc2 slmname=5arcsec_wide`
- `wait4ao on`
- `bash HWP_Rotation_Sequence.sh HWP_CYCLES=[NUM_CYCLES]`

End of Night / Re-Set to Standard NIRC2 Operations

If you are handing observations over to another NIRC2 observer, take the following steps to put NIRC2 back in its non-polarimetric configuration:

- Move the PCU out of the way with `modify -s pcu2 PCUNAME=home` or using the PCU Sequencer GUI (the latter is only available on k2aoserver).
- Remove the 5x10" mask with `modify -s nirc2 slmname='wide_clear'`
- Remove the Wollaston with `filter 17 17` (sets to clear + clear – see [FAQ](#) for a complete listing of filter and mask options)

If you are the last observer of the night and no further daytime calibrations with NIRC2 are needed, run the end of night commands (`endnight` in the command line).

Data Processing

Accessing Data via KOA

NIRC2-Pol data is stored on KOA and can be accessed using standard procedures for the observatory archive.

NIRC2-Pol DRP

Information coming soon.

HWP Fast Axis Determination

As described in [Fast Axis Orientation Verification](#), it is occasionally necessary to verify the orientation of the HWP fast axis due to the frequent removal/re-installation of this optic. The fast axis also varies slightly with wavelength. On the [NIRC2Pol-Ops GitHub](#), there is both a script for taking the requisite calibration sequence (`Fast_Axis_Cal_Sequence.sh`) and a Jupyter notebook for fitting the fast axis from that data (`fast_axis_cal_analysis.ipynb`). The fast axis is determined by finding the maximum of the modulation curve. See below for recent best fit fast axis values in different bands:

Observation Date	Band	Best Fit Fast Axis (deg)
2025 Sept 15	J	39.8
2025 Oct 02	H	43.6
2025 Oct 03	K	45.5
2025 Nov 21	J	40.7

About the Mueller Matrix Model

[insert background about Mueller Matrix modeling or eventually link to Rebecca's upcoming SPIE proceeding]

The Mueller Matrix model was last updated [DATE].

A list of all internal calibration data sets and standard star observations can be found here:

[+ NIRC2-Pol Polarimetric Calibration Standards and Internal Calibrations](#) .

Troubleshooting/FAQ

The EPICS/KTL keywords for the PCU2 (or the keywords for the rotation stage) aren't working.

First, make sure that you are on a terminal that has access to these commands (see the [FAQ "On which Keck machine...?"](#)). If you get a "channel not found" error for the PCU2, you can try rebooting the rotator with `caput k2:ao:pcu:rot:reb 1` on k2aoserver-new. Then, follow these instructions to see if the PCU rotator IOC is running properly and to reinitialize it if needed.

On k2obsao@k2aoserver-new, check if the PCU2 Rotator IOC is running with `screen -ls | grep pcu`. If you do not have access to k2aoserver, ask someone from the NIRC2-Pol team, or the OA/SA.

- A. If the IOC is running (see below for example of what this looks like), you should be good to proceed
 - a. `75357.pcu_seq_IOC (Detached)`
 - b. `71410.pcuIOC (Detached)`
 - c. `153597.pcu_rot_IOC (Detached)`
- B. If none of the IOCs are running, open the PCU Sequencer GUI; this will initialize all three.
- C. If only the rotator isn't running (i.e. you do not see `pcu_rot_IOC`), then run `k2pcu_rot.scr` which will launch the program in a new [screen instance](#). Disconnect from this screen instance with `ctrl + A` then D. If you need to reconnect to that screen instance for any reason, you can use `screen -x pcu_rot_IOC`.

Why is it taking so long for a single exposure?

Using `goi` can be quite slow when NIRC2 is already running slowly (which happens sometimes, due to the age of the instrument/electronics). This is because it checks that all the stages are in the right place and *not* moving. If you feel fairly confident that no stages should be in motion, you can use `goi -s` to bypass these checks and speed things up.

Even with the shortest exposure my target is saturating. What are the guidelines for subwindowing?

NIRC2 does not have any ND filters, so the usual way to observe particularly bright targets is to subarray the detector to get a shorter minimum exposure time. With NIRC2-Pol, it may be helpful to subarray only in the x direction, as the split from the Wollaston is in the y direction. [A table in the NIRC2 documentation](#) shows the minimum exposure times and allowed subarray dimensions. You can check the maximum value of your PSF in the NIRC2 quicklook GUI with the Gaussian fit tool; after changes to NIRC2's gain in recent years, saturation occurs around 4000 counts. We recommend choosing fainter standard stars to avoid this problem entirely if at all possible. For polarimetric standards, where a clean PSF isn't crucial, you can also open the AO loops to spread out the light on the detector.

It doesn't look like I'm getting any light to NIRC2-Pol, or the signal is really faint.

After you've checked the basics (are the dome lights on, if I'm taking flats? Is the AO hatch open? Is the NIRC2 shutter open?) – there are a number of moveable optics on the K2 AO bench that may be in the way of NIRC2-Pol. Ideally, you will have cleared these things during setup, but if something looks awry, look to these usual suspects: the KPIC dichroic (DFB) and another mirror on the bench (ISM). On k2aoserver-new, these can all be moved with the SC GUI. The keywords for these optics are `OBDBNAME` and `OBIMNAME`. They should be set to `home`.

On which Keck machine should I be running these different scripts, GUIs, and commands?

The NIRC2-Pol team has scripts that run on both k2aoserver-new (generally used for AO development) and waikoko-new (the standard NIRC2 observer terminal). EPICS commands and KTL keywords are available on k2aoserver-new. KTL keywords (and EPICS commands, but only with some extra effort) are available on waikoko-new. KTL keywords are *not* yet on vm-nirc2. Currently, the PCU Sequencer GUI, the SC GUI (for optics like the DFB, ISM, and image rotator), and the PCU2 start-up scripts are only available on k2aoserver.

Why can't I just use the `filt` command instead of `filter`?

As of 2025 Nov 24, the `filt` command removes the Wollaston while moving the wavelength filter into place. Lower level commands like `modify -s nirc2 fwiname [filter]` are not recommended, and do not update the NIRC2 status GUI or the `FILT` header keyword to accurately reflect which filters are selected. The `filter` command ensures that both the inner and outer filter wheels are where you want them, and that the GUI and FITS headers are properly updated to avoid confusion.

What if I need to take NIRC2-Pol calibrations *outside* of regular observing (i.e. daytime-only engineering)?

~1 week before (absolute minimum 1 day before), [request access via this procedure](#).

When you are ready to take data, log into k2aoserver-new—from a Keck VPN or on the Keck network you can run `k2obsao@k2aoserver-new` from a terminal, or if you have the remote observing software installed you can do `start_keck_viewers k2obsao`. A password is required—Briley, Rebecca, Max, and the Keck AO team have this. From there, you can use EPICS channels or the PCU Sequencer to command the PCU2 and a waikoko-new terminal for NIRC2 commands. Make sure to `modify -s nirc2plus PROGNAME=ENG` so that this engineering data will be properly saved and made public on KOA.

Who do I contact if I run into trouble with NIRC2-Pol?

If you need assistance beyond what the SAs/OAs can provide, or if you have questions outside of an observing run, please contact Max Millar-Blanchaer maxmb@ucsb.edu, Rebecca Zhang manxuanzhang@ucsb.edu, and Briley Lewis brileylewis@ucsb.edu. If desired, we can join your observation time to support your NIRC2-Pol use—please email us ahead of the night to let us know if you would like one of us present.

If I need to use the cal fiber on the lower Z stage of the PCU2, where should I put it for NIRC2-Pol observations?

Use the named position `nirc2` (*not* `optnirc2`!). This may be useful for testing QACITS and other coronagraph centering operations.

I'm taking flats and the GUI says the lamps are on, but it does *not* look like it in my images!

If the lamps do not seem to be on after using the GUI, try the command line approach:
`modify -s dcs flimagin=0 flspectr=1` turns on the spectral lamps and
`modify -s dcs flimagin=0 flspectr=0` turns them off.

Where can I find more information on the PCU2 and its use for distortion calibration?

The PCU2 Distortion Calibration team has [documentation here](#) and a [“cookbook” for how to take a distortion measurement here](#).

Why can't I use the wide or medium cameras on NIRC2 with polarimetry?

The Wollaston prism has a fixed splitting angle, so with the wide or medium cameras, you'll just have a lot of unused detector real estate (see below, with the wide camera on the left and the narrow camera on the right).

Figure 7: NIRC2 images with the Wollaston in using the wide camera (left) and narrow camera (right), illustrating why the narrow camera is recommended for NIRC2-Pol.

Why is data processing with the vortex complicated?

Vortex coronagraphs are effectively spatially-varying HWPs. Therefore, vortex coronagraphs alter the polarization vector of incoming light, requiring additional processing using knowledge of the alterations imposed by the vortex. The NIRC2-Pol team is actively working on designing data reduction capabilities for vortex coronagraphs with polarimetry.

Why should I use the largehex mask when observing?

NIRC2 has multiple pupil masks to obscure the secondary, spiders, and edges of the primary mirror. The largehex mask blocks the least amount of light while still completely covering the secondary. Accordingly, we recommend using this for all observations, except when using the vortex coronagraph; for the vortex, use fixedhex, which is optimized for vortex coronagraphy (see vortex documentation in the [NIRC2 Observer's Manual](#)). See below for illustrations of each pupil mask available, and [a later FAQ](#) for the positions of each in the pupil mask wheel.

Figure 8: The footprints of various pupil masks available on NIRC2. Credit: [Cosens et al. 2020](#)

Can you explain the rotator modes and how they relate to AO.OBRT?

The keyword AO.OBRT describes the physical angle of the image rotator (K mirror) relative to the AO bench. This is useful for polarimetric calibration, and is the relevant quantity for polarimetric efficiency. When using NIRC2 for daytime calibrations / dome flats, you can set this keyword directly with `modify -s ao obrt=45`. However, when tracking on sky, you *cannot* directly modify OBRT, as the tracking routines take precedence.

If you need the K mirror at a specific location on sky (e.g. for sky flat calibrations), you will need to set it to stationary with `rotate X stationary`, where *X* is the “rotation destination” in sky coordinates. This command (referred to as ROTCMD) is related to AO.OBRT as follows: $ROTCMD = (AO.OBRT * 2) - 0.7$. The factor of two translates between sky and bench coordinates, and the 0.7 is the NIRC2 instrument angle correction (INSTANGL).

What do I do if NIRC2 crashes?

First, if a HWP cycle script is running, kill it by exiting during the HWP rotation (instead of aborting a NIRC2 exposure). Then try launching the recovery script by either typing `recover` into the command line or selecting the recovery script from the NIRC2 background menu. If this does not work, you can check out [this troubleshooting page](#) or try to restart the Archon controller with `power_cycle_archon`.

How do I put a non-sidereal target in my star list?

To add a non-sidereal target, you will need to look up its position at the desired observation times with an ephemeris (e.g. [JPL Horizons](#)). In the Keck star list tool, create multiple entries for the target’s position at half hour intervals around when you want to observe it (e.g. “Io 8:30 UTC”), with the coordinates at those times pulled from the ephemeris. If observing a target where there may be multiple objects in field (like a Galilean moon), it may be helpful to have a viewing chart on hand to help the OA identify the correct object.

What lives in each filter wheel / slider on NIRC2?

All NIRC2 parameters can be viewed while on waikoko-new with the command `gshow -s nirc2` – we have also included tables below.

NIRC2 Inner Filter Wheel (FWINAME)

Filter Name	Filter Position	Notes
J	1	
H	2	
CH4_short	3	

CH4_long	4	
Y	5	
Ks	6	
Kp	7	
PaGamma	8	
K	9	
z	10	
H2O_ice	11	
PK50_1.5	12	Very wide band filter; may not behave well with AO
18hole_msk	13	
Lw	14	
Lp	15	
Ms	16	
clear	17	default
Hel_A	18	

NIRC2 Outer Filter Wheel (FWONAME)

*Note: as the Wollaston is located in this wheel and **must** be in for NIRC2-Pol, none of the other filters in this wheel can be used with polarimetry. See [Available Modes](#) for more info.*

Filter Name	Filter Position	Notes
Bra_cont	1	
Jcont	2	
PaBeta	3	
Hcont	4	
Fell	5	
He1_B	6	
H2_1-0	7	

Br_gamma	8	
H2_2-1	9	
Kcont	10	
CO_2-0_bh	11	
PAH	12	
9holeMsk	13	
Wollaston	14	Required for polarimetry
PK50_1.5	15	
PK50_1.0	16	
clear	17	default
Br_alpha	18	

NIRC2 Slit Mask Slider (SLMNAME)

Mask Name	Mask Position	Notes
slot	1	
narrow_clear	2	
medium_clear	3	
wide_clear	4	Default / where to reset for standard NIRC2 obs
wide_edge	5	
5arcsec_wide	6	Required for polarimetry
5arcsec_slot	7	

NIRC2 Grism Slider (GRSNAME)

Grism Name	Grism Position	Notes
empty	1	
medres	2	

clear	3	
lowres	4	
lens	5	

NIRC2 Pupil Mask Wheel (PMSNAME)

Mask Name	Mask Position	Notes
incircle	1	
smallhex	2	
fixedhex	3	Recommended for vortex coronagraphy
mediumhex	4	
largehex	5	Recommended for general observations
open	6	

NIRC2 Coronagraph and Slit Slider (SLSNAME)

Filter Name	Filter Position	Notes
corona100	1	
corona400	2	
corona150	3	
corona1000	4	
corona600	5	
corona1500	6	
corona800	7	
corona2000	8	
corona200	9	
corona300	10	
slit10	11	

slit20	12	
slit30	13	
slit40	14	
slit60	15	
slit80	16	
slit120	17	
slit160	18	
clear	19	
vortexk	20	
vortexcen	21	
vortexlm	22	